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Examining Inclusive pedagogy and practice: Moroccan primary teachers' attitudes and practices in Moroccan Primary Schools

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Abstract

Inclusive schooling is a recent phenomenon in the Moroccan educational system. It is about giving all schoolchildren equal instructive prospects and opportunities in conventional classrooms. Schools are social institutions that should improve all students' lives through appropriate teaching and learning practices. However, the school culture is vital for the improvement of inclusive education. This study aimed to explore primary teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards inclusive education practice in supporting students with disabilities in Moroccan primary schools. In order to achieve this aim, this study takes on qualitative analysis to gather and analyse the data and present the results. Thematic content analysis was used for analysing qualitative data collected via semi-structured interviews. Ten interviews were conducted with ten teachers from Moroccan primary schools. The qualitative data showed that teachers support inclusive schooling; however, they hesitated to include students with severe disabilities. Several factors influenced Moroccan primary teachers' attitudes towards inclusive education. The most common factors were: 1) inadequate training of teachers on teaching students with disabilities. 2) Lack of suitable equipment to support students and teachers in the teaching and learning process, 3) inadequate government funding, 4) limited pledge from the Moroccan Ministry of Education, and inadequate contribution and meeting of teachers on policy and curriculum proposals were also identified as causative influences for non-inclusion of students with debilities in conventional schools.

Keywords: Inclusive Pedagogy; Inclusive Education; Teacher Training; Learning Process; Students with Disabilities

1. Introduction

Bestowing to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities (2007), disabled people must be included in all aspects of life. The agreement sets out the wide-ranging principles, including non-discrimination, equality of opportunity, respect for difference and acceptance of individuals with infirmities as part of human assortment and humanity, and full operative participation. One of the foremost goals of inclusive education is to ensure that students with disabilities have fair and equal access to conventional schools. This depends on changes and amendments in schools and mainstream classrooms [17], [11]. Yet, the objectives of inclusive schooling will not be accomplished speedily, and the process itself will take time to evolve and develop. Studies show that inclusive education offers social development for all students and improves educational opportunities. It also responds to diversity, fosters understanding and tolerance and helps to eradicate biases and favouritism against students with disabilities [24].

Research displays that students with disabilities achieve great success at academic and social education levels compared to those with disabilities in different particular education institutions [26]. In the same vein, [14] agrees that the education of students with disabilities is easily accessible to the general curriculum. The majority of children with disabilities do not achieve better progress in education when isolated.

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This means acceptance of all students and appreciation for their rights in education, regardless of differences among them. In the views of [15] and [26], inclusive education is progressively seen as a plan for responding to the diversity of students in schools at both national and international levels. According to [5], with the increasing variety of children in schools worldwide, old models of separating students by different categories and labels are intimidating and domineering.

1.1. Problems of the Study

The registration of students with disabilities in conventional schools did not provide equal opportunities to learn with their mainstream peers and did not help them with social and educational growth [1]. Educating students with special needs in conventional schools is a right assured under special legislation for the disabled (Ibid). Local, regional and global legislation can ensure the development of teachers and the development of a positive attitude toward inclusive education. The attitude toward the education of these students plays a critical role and is essential to the success of the integration programme and to improving positive relations with individuals [19]. However, the indicators in the educational field do not disclose an acceptable level of trends and perspectives amongst teachers working with these students. This is mismatched with the worldwide direction encouraging the rights of students with special schooling needs, including the disabled, to live within their community and the calls to integrate them into mainstream schools and the community (ibid).

Based on the above, the problem of the study is that there is no explicit knowledge of teachers' views towards inclusive education. Despite the global trend and the ongoing quest to apply the process of inclusive education, the current study explores teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards inclusive schooling practice in supporting students with disabilities in Moroccan primary schools and considers the significant problems with inclusive education.

1.2. Research Aim

This study aims to determine whether Moroccan primary teachers understand the concept of inclusive education. It also explores their perceptions and attitudes towards inclusive education practice in supporting students with disabilities in Moroccan primary schools. This study also establishes the underlying factors influencing Moroccan primary teachers' perspectives and attitudes towards inclusion education.

2. Review of Literature

According to [30], including disabled students in mainstream schools and classrooms is part of a more significant global human rights movement that advocates for the full inclusion of all people with disabilities in all aspects of life. Similarly, the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization [32] urges all governments to implement inclusive policies and enrol all students with disabilities in mainstream schools [33]. This is because students with disabilities are frequently excluded from mainstream education.

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2007) ratified and reinforced calls for all people with disabilities to be included in all aspects of life. Non-discrimination, equality of opportunity, respect for difference, and acceptance of persons with disabilities as part of human diversity and humanity, and fully effective participation of persons with disabilities are stated in 'Article 1' of the convention (UNESCO, 2009). However, this chapter covers the literature about the foci of this research. That is, to explore teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards inclusive education practice in supporting students with disabilities in Moroccan primary schools.

Inclusive education, according to the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [34] is defined as:

"A process of addressing and responding to all learners' diverse needs through inclusive practices in learning, cultures, and societies and reducing exclusion within and from education." It entails changes and modifications in content, approaches, structures, and strategies, with a shared vision that encompasses all children of the appropriate age range and believes that it is the mainstream system's responsibility to educate all children." [31].

According to [7], some professionals support full inclusion where all children are served in the mainstream classroom. Studies show that mainstream schools are favoured and have the most appropriate settings for all students (ibid). Comparative studies also found better results for students in mainstream settings than in special schools [13]. Professionals who support the inclusion of students with disabilities in mainstream schools consider that all students have a right to completely inclusive educational practices where they can benefit from being included in a school setting with their peers [7]. However, other professionals disagree that full inclusion, where students with disabilities are given

all their education in a mainstream education setting, is not enough to support students with more severe academic, emotional, social or physical [7].

[3] stresses that increasing means in special education will be based on the ideas and practices of special education and will, as a result, involve limited changes in mainstream education to cater for disabled children. According to [28], these include not only those students with a disability but also those students with learning difficulties and behavior disorders, those from culturally and linguistically different backgrounds, those with chronic medical conditions, and all those who are at risk in the school environment for whatever reasons.

Inclusive education involves overcoming practices that segregate throughout the education system. [3] says that educating children in segregated environments and requiring them to follow different courses of study from their peers in terms of content and learning environment is not inclusion. With inclusion, efforts are made to ensure that the needs of all students are met within an equitable and accepting education system (Ibid). Several studies have been conducted on teachers and their approach to inclusive education and the alleged benefits and drawbacks of teaching all students in a general class [6], [29]. According to [6], this has revealed the views of teachers of education that inclusive education affects their adoption of the concept. However, trained teachers are exposed to inclusive education, and the practice of inclusion establishes an enhanced approach concerning inclusive learners.

3. Research Methodology

The interpretive epistemological position was chosen because of the nature of this study. This approach was chosen because the researcher's goal is centred on understanding, rather than on predicting, what the participants in the research study believed, and how they felt and interpreted the events about inclusive education? Disability, culture, teaching and classroom management in Moroccan primary schools. Qualitative content analysis was adopted, including the ten individual face-to-face interviews used to collect data from 20 Moroccan primary teachers from three different special schools. This sample (N = 10) does not represent the overall population, but it is broad enough to give valuable insights into a range of insights. These participants were chosen because of their central role in inclusive education.

Choosing an appropriate method to address research questions is a significant part of the research. It guides the research design in selecting a suitable methodology. As a result, qualitative research methods will be used to produce and collect relevant data in light of this work's investigative and inductive nature and achieve the goals. Qualitative methods are appropriate when the study's objectives need in-depth insight into the study. The nature of the enquiry questions in this work was mainly about Moroccan primary teachers' views and perceptions of inclusive education. Therefore, it will be easy for the researcher to obtain data about Moroccan primary teachers' inclusive education programmes at these schools.

The researcher was concerned about selecting an appropriate participant sample size in order to ensure accurate population representation. In qualitative studies, the sampling is strategic [21]. It is essential to choose informants that are most likely to have much information to share on the theme in question and represent as wide a social interaction as possible [16]. [21] defines sampling as the act, process, or technique of selecting a representative part of a population to determine the parameters or characteristics of the whole population. The concept of the research subject is related to the question of what and who will be investigated.

The researcher had a broad range of interview subjects selecting Moroccan primary teachers. These were primarily chosen as they were people known to the researcher and their friends. These participants also provided rich, varied and in-depth data because of their high experience levels. Samples aim to represent the population with similar proportions of people regarding age, gender, class and ethnicity.

The research population was relatively small, and time was limited when the data was collected. In addition, the numbers of people teaching disabled students were relatively small. Thus obtaining the opportunity to interview them was difficult and therefore piloting was not an option. Firstly, selected participants were assumed to have been teaching during the study. Secondly, most of the participants had been teaching in Moroccan primary schools for several years. Hence, as shown in table (1) below, they were more knowledgeable about the research contexts and the students with disabilities.

Table 1 Background Data of the Interviewees

Teachers	Gender	Age	Qualifications	Teaching Experience	Disability Experience	Disability of Students in Class
P1	M	45	Bachelor	20	Yes	Physical disability
P2	F	51	Bachelor	28	Yes	Speech impairment
P3	F	34	Bachelor	12	Yes	Learning disability
P4	M	39	Bachelor	17	Yes	Hearing impairment
P5	F	33	Bachelor	10	No	Down syndrome
P6	F	53	Bachelor	30	Yes	Visual impairment
P7	M	42	Bachelor	20	Yes	Visual impairment
P8	F	37	Bachelor	15	Yes	Speech impairment
P9	M	31	Bachelor	9	No	Down syndrome
P10	F	47	Bachelor	27	Yes	Learning disability

The researcher obtained information that would not have been available if questionnaires or other forms had been used. As a result, interviews are deemed appropriate for this research. The interview consisted of carefully designed questions regarding wording and sequence for this research. These include face-to-face. All interviews were conducted between September and January 2021 in Morocco.

Before the interviews, the participants were asked to fill in a demographic information sheet using tick boxes. This included a list of variables such as information about age, years of teaching experience and disabilities of children they had worked with. While giving out the form, the researcher assured the participants that information gathered on the record would remain confidential and not be used to identify them. With all this research data recorded on tapes, the researcher transcribed all the taped material gathered the same day that each interview was completed. Transliterating the data after every interview helped the researcher formulate further questions that he thought were important and relevant. These questions were carried over for the next teacher to be interviewed. All data were transcribed in detail.

4. Data Analysis

Analysing research data in a qualitative study is an ongoing process throughout the data collection period. [25] describe qualitative data analysis as a cyclical process in which data collection affects data analysis. This study aimed to explore Moroccan primary teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards inclusive education practice in supporting students with disabilities in Moroccan schools. As mentioned previously, a qualitative approach will be used to achieve the aim of the study. However, qualitative data analysis is remarkably different from the statistical study, as the data does not appear to be in a quantitative form [25]. Content analysis forms a structure to establish open-ended information (ibid). More details about the content analysis forms are presented in the following section, which offers a comprehensive description of how content analysis is used in this research.

4.1. Thematic Analysis of Qualitative Data Obtained in the Interviews

The feedback from the interviewees was placed under the main themes. This section combines the data obtained from the ten teachers' perceptions during fieldwork into themes and sub-themes within which the participants' perceptions have been identified.

4.1.1. Moroccan Primary Teachers' Understanding of Inclusive Education Concepts

This study revealed that Moroccan primary teachers held diverse personal views and understanding about what constitutes inclusive education and disabilities. [8] found that these teachers' ideas and knowledge of inclusive education concepts influenced their implementation of inclusive programmes. However, in this study, teachers' understanding of concepts varied. Depending on whether they had been exposed to the terms before. It was revealed that teachers who had attended universities and had further study opportunities were most able to define and explain what constitutes inclusive education

Table (1) shows the number of Moroccan primary teachers who had received training in teaching students with disabilities and those who had not received any formal training. As shown in table (1), most teachers (N=10) did not receive any training in teaching students with disabilities, and only two teachers had received training. In this context, the interviews revealed that most of the respondents strongly believed that the lack of good training is a negative factor and that providing good training would be a positive factor in implementing inclusive education, and that training should be made available.

It was evident that most teachers who had been introduced to inclusive education concepts either through their university training, further study opportunities, or in-service training could define inclusive education concepts more appropriately than those who had no idea at all before the current study. This is illustrated in the words of the following respondents:

“Inclusive education is about students who have disabilities or do not belong to the mainstream; they stay together with mainstream students in the same classroom, where we teach them all similarly and study together to live together.” (P8)

“Inclusive education means bringing students together or putting them alongside in the same school where they can learn with the mainstream students. Those students with special needs can learn together with the mainstream ones.” (P3)

Most teachers who had attended inclusive education training understood the concept whereby all students were brought together in the same school/classroom and taught. Thus, [20] argued that training is essential for promoting inclusive education. However, in the current study, although teachers had gone through some form of training in inclusive education, the implementation aspect at the school and classroom level was lacking. One reason was a lack of continuity through staff development programmes [4]. Another reason was that the school leadership was not proactive in fostering inclusion [10]. Teachers often took their prior learning for granted, and therefore, their ideas were not implemented at the school and classroom levels [9]. This grim situation was contrary to other inclusive studies found, where training positively influenced the inclusion of students with disabilities in inclusive classrooms [35].

Conversely, teachers who had little or no knowledge about inclusive education concepts were confused when defining the terms. This group of staff members explained the concepts of training, education and seeing people with disabilities in their communities and schools. The study suggests that teacher education and professional development programmes focusing on inclusive education were neglected. Through teacher in-service training and preparedness, full inclusion is reported to be successful [2]. However, this was not the case in the schools that participated in the study. It was revealed that teacher education was minimal or, in most cases, non-existent. Due to the teachers' lack of understanding of the basic concepts of inclusive education, they appeared less able to cater for the specific needs of students with disabilities in mainstream schools/classrooms (Baltes et al., (2006); therefore, it was strongly argued that in order for inclusive education to be successful, teachers should be trained in how to modify the classroom structures, curriculum differentiation, and selection of appropriate teaching and assessment strategies.

4.1.2. Teachers' Perspectives on Inclusion of Students.

This section focuses on the study's findings concerning the first part of the first research question: what teachers' perspectives and attitudes affect the inclusion or exclusion of students with disabilities in their schools or classrooms? All of the 10 participants who took part in the interviews supported inclusive education. However, they all agreed that students with profound disabilities should be educated in unique education settings. Students with profound disabilities need more care and management, and those who need planned support such as wheelchairs to help with their movement around the school.

Teachers interviewed showed that some factors have been identified as to why not all students with disabilities should be included in mainstream schools. These factors include communication barriers, differences in teaching styles, lack of available support teachers and unavailability of appropriate equipment and resources. Most of the teachers in this study said that the idea of inclusion was perfect. Because it broadened the minds of students with disabilities, it also gave them an idea of what was happening.

Five other teachers had negative attitudes towards educational programmes. Concerning this point, one of the teachers made the following point:

“Only the students who can cope and be involved in academic activities should be included in the mainstream schools.” (P4)

His view was also confirmed by another teacher who stated that:

“Not all students could be included in mainstream schools, so special schools should still be there to meet the educational requirements of students who have profound disabilities.” (P7)

Three teachers had negative attitudes towards communication. Concerning this point, one of the teachers made the following point:

“With students who were deaf and mute and were intellectually impaired, communication would be a barrier. Unless the teaching style in mainstream classrooms changed, students with disabilities would not have their needs met very well”. (P2)

Differences in pedagogical styles used in mainstream schools and special schools were cited as one of the reasons why students with severe disabilities should be educated in unique educational settings. As one teacher said:

“The way students with disabilities were taught in the special education and how they were taught in the mainstream schools were quite different. In the special schools, teaching is mostly one to one interaction whereas in the mainstream it is a whole class teaching approach”. (P9)

In general, teachers' perspectives on the inclusion of students with disabilities were examined during the interviews. This research showed that all the teachers supported inclusive education and agreed that inclusive education was good. However, all the teachers said that students with severe disabilities should be educated in special education settings. The ability to cope in mainstream schools was shown in the study to be a crucial influence on the inclusion of students with disabilities in Moroccan Primary schools. The majority of the teachers said that only the students who could cope and be involved in academic activities should be included in the conventional schools.

Inclusive education means the full inclusion of students with diverse abilities in all aspects of schooling and that schools should accommodate all students regardless of their abilities or disabilities [11]. The literature shows that all students, no matter how severe their disabilities are or how intensive their needs are, belong in the general education classroom and can be accommodated in the mainstream class in their neighbourhood schools. They would be attending school if they did not have a disability [24], [7]. There is also sufficient research evidence to suggest that inclusion even of students with the most severe disabilities can work if schools have a culture of shared values and are genuinely committed to improving their practices [17].

4.1.3. Barriers to Inclusive Education

Many barriers have been identified related to the inclusion of students with disabilities in conventional schools, such as type and severity of the disability, lack of teacher training, lack of specialist teachers, extra workload and responsibility of teachers, lack of government funding, limited commitment from the Ministry of Education, inadequate school facilities and lack of appropriate equipment and resources.

According to the interview data, all the teachers identify the type and severity of disability as one factor that has affected the inclusion of students with disabilities in conventional schools. Three teachers said that these schools are known as the schools for speech impairment and hearing impairment. However, the schools only accept students who have speech impairments and hearing impairments. The following extract is representative of this:

“The school only accepts students with speech and hearing impairment, so students with other disabilities were referred to other special schools that suited their disabilities”. (P10)

All the teachers said that their schools only accepted students with mild disabilities. As one teacher noted:

“A student with a mild disability is a student whose disability does not affect his or her achievement largely and is not significant. For example, the child does not need any equipment at school”. (P8)

However, this research found that schools accepted students depending on the type of disability they had and the severity of their disabilities. These findings from the interviews have confirmed previous results from the literature review. For example, [2] and [23] observed that the nature and severity of students' needs and disabilities strongly influenced teachers' disposition toward inclusive practices.

4.1.4. Lack of Teacher Training.

This research found that teachers' training at their respective teacher training institutions was inadequate in teaching students with disabilities. The interview data suggested that teacher training was a factor in teachers' negative attitudes

towards including students with disabilities in schools. Most teachers said they should receive education and training to implement inclusive education. This study showed that all the teachers held a Bachelor's degree. However, no teachers were specifically teaching students with disabilities, and they lacked the qualifications to familiarise students with disabilities in schools. However, when teachers were asked if they had ever been involved in any training courses or received this training. For example, in the context of the lack of training, one of the teachers stated that:

"I have been in this school for 15 years, but I have not been sent for further studies or training on inclusive education". (P10)

Although some of the teachers had training in teaching students with disabilities, as shown in table (2), the teachers said the course did not prepare them sufficiently for the reality they faced with students with disabilities in their class. As one teacher said:

"Throughout our training, special education was being introduced. But the content was mostly on special education in general. There is no mention of how to deal with students with disabilities in the classroom". (P3)

Another teacher stated:

"No training in teaching students with disabilities at all, so just taught the students with disabilities the same way I taught the non-disabled students in my class. I interacted with the students, so we began to understand them and learned how to teach them better". (P6)

The study suggests that teacher education and professional development programmes focusing on inclusive education were neglected. Through teacher in-service training and preparedness, full inclusion is reported to be successful [2], [27]. However, this was not the case in the schools that participated in the study. It was revealed that teacher education and professional development were minimal or, in most cases, non-existent. Due to the teachers' lack of understanding of the basic concepts of special and inclusive education, they appeared less able to cater for the specific needs of students with disabilities in mainstream schools/classrooms [29].

4.1.5. Lack of government funding

One of the most shared arguments against the movement toward inclusion in education is financial and resource consideration [18]. The challenge of these arguments is the development of effective financial strategies that would support inclusive education because inclusive education is a part of the educational system or an additional government programme. Therefore, making provision for inclusion will blow the education budget and increase the unit of cost provision. It is common sense that those with more severe and complex needs will require additional resources because they have to fulfil their educational needs. [19] agree that inclusion is expensive to implement at the first stage but should become cost-effective. They get their right to education and the necessary education to live a dignified life with inclusive education. The extended term will pay off to avoid dependency costs for families, communities, and societies.

Lack of government funding was identified in this research as a contributing factor to the reluctance of schools and teachers to have students with disabilities in their schools and classrooms. One of the teachers mentioned that:

"Without the government support and extra funding, the process of inclusive education in Moroccan primary schools will take longer to achieve than anticipated. Teachers predicted that it would take longer for inclusive education to materialise in Moroccan primary schools and for students with incapacities to be fully included in all schools in Moroccan primary schools". (P2)

Another teacher said

"Disabled students require additional government resources and assistance. We need more teaching staff and purchase appropriate resources or construct additional classrooms to accommodate all students with disabilities. Schools will require additional funding to restructure their school buildings to accommodate students with visual impairments and students in wheelchairs. Because of financial difficulties and lack of funding, schools will find it hard to restructure and make their schools conducive to the needs of students with disabilities". (P6)

4.1.6. Inadequate pledge from the Ministry of Education

With inadequate funding from the government, the Ministry of Education also had limited funds and human resources to visit schools and monitor the inclusion of students with disabilities. Teachers noted limited commitment from the Ministry of Education as a contributing factor to the non-inclusion of students with disabilities in their schools. Since

the Ministry of Education in Morocco failed to visit the schools to monitor the education of students with disabilities, schools and teachers did not see it as a priority to include these students.

All of the teachers in primary schools and secondary schools said education officials from the Ministry of Education rarely visited the schools to see how schools were progressing with the education of students with disabilities. There was no monitoring or evaluation of how successful inclusion was. No special attention was paid to students with disabilities. As one teacher said:

“So far, no one from the Ministry of Education had visited our schools to see if there were any students with disabilities. Before inclusive education is officially implemented in all schools, the officers in the Ministry of Education should themselves be committed and be aware of what inclusive education is all about. The Ministry of Schooling should consult teachers and listen to the recommendations before integrating all students with disabilities into conventional schools”. (P9)

This aligns with [12], asserting that those in authority in the education hierarchy leave the issues to the teachers to look after, without follow-up to determine the practice’s efficacy.

4.1.7. Inadequate School Facilities

The challenge for government and schools to successfully implement inclusive education is making the situation conducive to teaching and learning. Therefore, to support that situation, the government should be providing all the facilities such as infrastructures, human resources and learning materials. This research found that schools did not have the appropriate facilities and provisions to include students with disabilities successfully. Teachers revealed that their schools did not have ramps or proper toilet facilities to accommodate students in wheelchairs. As the teacher mentioned:

“Many schools have been built without any consideration for students with disabilities. The school environments are not contributing to and welcoming students with disabilities”. (P10)

This research also found that students with disabilities were often neglected during certain class activities because of the lack of appropriate equipment and resources. Students with disabilities needed extensive resources and equipment to help them learn. Another teacher also said:

With the lack of proper equipment, students with disabilities at our school did not contribute to Physical Education or sports because the school does not have the right sports equipment to include them. The students preferred to stay in the classroom, and they did something else while the rest of the students went out for outdoor activities. (P9)

The inclusion process in many countries will take a long time to improve because of a lack of resources [22]. For teachers to do their work effectively, adequate and appropriate resources must be available. Many students with severe disabilities rely on assistive technology to aid their movements and learning. This research shows no indication of any technology for students with disabilities in the mainstream schools, such as computers, to assist students in their learning. Nearly all the teachers who took part in the interviews made similar comments about the nonexistence of inclusive education policies.

5. Limitations of the Study

As with any investigation project, this study has a certain number of limitations that should be considered by those using this study’s findings or evaluating the results. Several limitations have affected the outcome of this study. Generally, a general challenge to all interpretive researchers is the need to triangulate. However, the researcher had to rely solely on semi-structured interviews; no observation or policy document analysis was conducted. This feature meant that the study incurred more limitations.

Only ten teachers were interviewed in this research, so this was a limitation regarding how comprehensive the information was. It was challenging to make generalisations based on the ten teachers’ insights. There was also no statistical data on the number of students with disabilities educated in conventional schools. Another limitation is related to the translation of data. The interviews with the teachers were conducted in Arabic and then translated into English. Even though the researcher paid considerable attention to the discussions’ translation and asked one of his associates to check the translated data, the process is not without its shortcomings. The researcher believes that it is impossible to have perfect translation and that there will always be particular meanings lost in translation. However,

he is confident that the translated data has faithfully captured the teachers' implications during the interviews. The data presented here do not misrepresent the teachers in any way.

6. Contributions and Implications of Study

Despite the limitations outlined above, the researcher believes that this study contributes to the relevant literature in many ways. Methodologically, this study shows the value of qualitative research as it uses interviews to study how and why teachers implement inclusive education at schools. In addition to contributions to instructive research in general, this research has several implications. This research suggests that there is a need for teachers who are unwilling to accept students with disabilities in their schools in Moroccan primary schools to change their perspectives and attitudes towards students with disabilities. They should become aware of the international trends and practices regarding inclusive education and the inclusion of all students with disabilities in schools.

Teachers had reservations about the inclusion of students with disabilities because schools were not appropriately structured and resourced to accommodate the educational needs and disabilities of the students. Inclusive education should be implemented in all schools. Students have the right to attend school in their community or at a school of their choice. The Ministry of Education needs to provide the necessary funding for implementation, adaptations and modifications to existing school structures, appropriate equipment and resources, and specialist teachers to ensure that all children with disabilities have access to education in schools within their neighborhoods and communities.

General Recommendations

While a broader and more intensive effort from all sectors of society is needed to promote inclusive education, three recommendations are suggested for action to improve the situation in schools towards fostering inclusive education in Moroccan primary schools. Firstly, adequate teachers' preparation should be considered through training. It should focus on inclusive education. This action is appropriate so that the teachers can understand the tenets and skills associated with inclusive education and disabilities. In so doing, the teachers can take ownership and be responsible for including students with disabilities in conventional schools and classrooms. Secondly, the teachers should use some teachers already in the schools who have qualifications, background and experience in special education, inclusive education, and disability. A survey needs to be done to identify these teachers who are already part of the education system to provide in-service training for other teachers and act as role models for these teachers towards fostering inclusive education. Thirdly, the work done by the Ministry of Education must be extended to all schools as part of staff job descriptions. This is because the government is lagging in resources, financial and human resource supply and support for achieving inclusive education.

7. Conclusion

While many research areas can be executed, three areas of concern were predominantly evident as a follow-up of the current study. Firstly, this study only explores the teachers' perceptions and attitudes towards inclusive education practice in supporting students with disabilities in Moroccan primary schools' cultural features and procedures that influenced inclusive education. An additional investigation needs to be done on how the school culture affects students' learning in inclusive classrooms in Morocco.

Second, the current study has identified a gap in the Ministry of Education's support for inclusive education, limited or non-existent. An investigation into how the Ministry of Education carries out its professional responsibilities in inclusive education should be conducted. Finally, teachers were found to have a limited understanding of what constitutes inclusive education. As a result, future research should examine how professional development can improve teachers' understanding and knowledge of inclusive education in schools and the impact of this training on inclusive education and teachers' practices.

Research should also be conducted on the impact of inclusive education for students with disabilities in Morocco. Several individuals with disabilities who were educated in mainstream Moroccan primary schools now hold prominent positions in the country. Their experiences and life stories may inspire students with disabilities, their families and teachers, and those who perceive students with disabilities as "uneducable" people who should only be educated in special schools. This research is also wished-for to inform the Ministry of Education in Morocco of the inclusive practices operating in schools that have already accommodated students with disabilities. It is hoped that the Ministry of Education may begin to bring positive changes within the current education system and encourage inclusive practices in all schools to benefit all students with disabilities.

This research is also significantly contributing to the international literature on inclusive education. Additionally, it can create a greater awareness of inclusive education and its importance for students with disabilities in Moroccan primary schools. It is hoped that teachers' perspectives and attitudes will help all stakeholders, including the Ministry of Education, parents, and school management in the Moroccan education system, improve their support for students with disabilities in schools.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author has no conflicts of interest to declare. The author alone is responsible for the content and writing of the paper.

Statement of informed consent

Informed approval was obtained from all participants involved in the study.

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